

THE USE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES TO OPTIMIZE THE MANAGEMENT OF HIGH-SPEED TRAINS

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Annotatsiya. On high-speed sites and sites with high intensity of movement of trains the organisation of a continuous radio covering and use of digital system of a radio communication is supposed. Tracking movement of high-speed trains is carried out in uniform dispatching control center of trains. On monitors of the dispatcher the scheme of the given site with the train image, and also co-ordinates of a train, its acceleration is displayed. In case of need falls or increases of speed the dispatcher directly contacts the train dispatcher. In case of a deviation of one of technical indicators, infringement of vigilance of the machinist, or other emergency situation, on the monitor of the dispatcher character of a deviation at once is displayed. The dispatcher contacts the train dispatcher, or with the machinist of the locomotive, with on duty on the nearest station and other necessary services. For example, such as, transfer of the following nearest arrow and train return into the way, emergency braking. For creation of fast and timely revealing of infringements, their preventions, constant control of a condition of high-speed and high-speed highways high-precision coordinate systems (HCS) on the basis of GLONASS/GPS will be created at use of differential amendments. For increase of reliability and accuracy of the information on a site of mobile units the onboard computer complex equipped with navigating systems should be used. Processing of the information from navigating systems is carried out directly in the onboard device. The obtained data about object position in real time is transferred on wireless channels GSM-R, satellite, LTE-R, etc.

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The dispatcher should provide the following control:

- Operative control in a mode of real time of geographical co-ordinates;
- Observance of safety requirements of train and shunting work;
- Control over creation of fast and timely revealing of infringements;

Control under certain circumstances, in due time to take measures under their prevention or the decision in case of already developed deviation.

High-speed movement of trains should support high level of safety.

That the nobility where approximately there is a train, whether it will arrive in time on station, it is possible to do without satellite technologies, it is enough to learn time of distribution of a signal to two nearest base stations. It will allow to define with ease co-ordinate of a train to within 100-150 meters but the matter is that on such high speeds as 300-350 km/h for complete control of safety in case of infringement of vigilance of the machinist, train passage on a forbidding signal of a traffic light, train departure on a counter way, lock-outs of an arrow to the operator will be necessary to take in few seconds measures under the emergency situation prevention.

In the early nineties the International union of the railways (IUR/UIC) at the initiative of a number of the European railways has started working out of the project of the European integrated advanced network of a railway radio communication (EIRENE - European Integrated Railway Radio Enhanced Network), called to replace Europe existing on the railways analogue radio systems multi-purpose appointments and to provide operational compatibility and a radio communication continuity at trans-European transportations. As the base standard for construction of the unified digital system of radio communication IUR standard GSM (Global System for Mobile Communication), confirmed by the European institute on standardization in the field of telecommunication (ETSI) has been accepted operating for popular networks of cellular communication. Standard GSM for systems of a radio communication of the railway transportation, named GSM-R (GSM for Railways), is a variant of standard GSM of version 2.5 to which technical specifications the changes considering specialized railway functions and the appendices are made. According to the changes brought in the standard in addition to the basic functions realized in networks of popular cellular communication, a network of standard GSM-R should provide according to operational requirements of the railways:

Circular calls (VBS, Voice Broadcast Services);

Group calls and communication in groups (VGCS, Voice Group Call Service);

Priority, emergency calls and management of priorities of calls (eMLPP, enhanced Multi-Level Precedence and Preemption);

Special kinds of addressing: functional addressing and addressing depending on a site of the subscriber.

Except specialized functions at the organization of radio telephone communication, a network of a radio communication of standard GSM-R provide realization of special supplements on the data transmission, systems of automatic control necessary for functioning with railway traffic (project ETCS L2, L3). The basic characteristics of a digital radio communication standard of GSM-R are resulted in table 1. 1.

Table 1. 1

The Basic characteristics digital systems of a radio communication of standard GSM-R

The name of parametres	Value of parametres
Range of working frequencies (transfer / reception), MHz	876 – 880 / 921 – 925
Duplex rating of frequencies, MHz	45
Total quantity of working frequencies	19
Rating between bearing frequencies, MHz	0, 2
Number of channels of the traffic, on 1 bearing / maximum, the channel	8 / 152
Access method	TDMA
Modulation kind	GMSK
Speed of data transmission, kbit/ps	9, 6
The general speed of transfer in a radio channel, kbit/ps	270, 833
Speed of transformation of speech kbit/ps	13 (6, 5)
The demanded relation a signal/hindrance	9 dB
Algorithm of speech coding	RPE-LTR

Despite advantages of digital standard GSM-R has lacks [9] which have been revealed at 15 summer operating experience GSM-R on the European railways, including the high-speed. The European railway agency (ERA - European Railway Agency) had been made the audit questionnaire. Answers to audit questions have been received from the organisations presented in table 1. 2.

Table 1. 2

The List of respondents of audit

Organisation kind	Countries
The manager of an infrastructure	Switzerland, Belgium, Germany, Finland, Sweden, Austria, France, the Czech republic, Great Britain, Slovakia, Italy, the Netherlands
National regulating body in the field of transport safety	Finland, Poland, the Czech republic, Germany, Spain, Great Britain, Lithuania, Italy, the Netherlands
The operator-carrier	Finland, Sweden, Norway, Austria, Finland, France, Germany, Italy, Great Britain
Suppliers	NSN (Nokia Siemens Network), Kapsch, Siemens
Others	RSSB - body on standardization in the field of railway safety (Great Britain)

By results of the spent audit the report [10] in which the data about refusals and failures TRC which was taking place at operation GSM-R is presented has been prepared, their consequences and opinion of the linear personnel on the substance of these consequences and possibilities of their prevention are analysed. In table 1. 3 the list of these refusals and failures is resulted.

All listed failures and refusals have the reasons presented in table 1. 4 which also contains the description of consequences of failures and refusals for traffic safety of trains. To exclude the specified consequences, such system of a radio communication is necessary, refusals and which failures should be shown to a minimum.

Table 1. 3
Refusals and failures at performance of basic functions
TRC of standard GSM-R

Refusals and failures of functions of a speech transmission	Refusals and failures of functions of data transmission
Failure at testing.	
Refusal in access to a telecommunication service.	
Problems of transfer of connection at crossing of national borders.	
Problems of registration of a rolling stock at crossing of national borders	
Erroneous emergency call.	Data transmission delay about a

<p>Refusal of transfer of an emergency call. Individual call, group call, interruption of group connection. Incorrect addressing by an individual call or emergency call DNC→TCHM (the train dispatcher → the machinist of the locomotive)</p>	route
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Table 1. 4
Refusals and failures in digital system PRS of standard GSM-R

Refusals and failures	The reasons	Consequences
Failure at testing	Malfunction of equipment TRC	Train delay at departure
Data transmission delay on a radio channel about a route	Channel GPRS failure	The delay of departure of a train has made 30 minutes
Erroneous emergency call	Defect of the cheloveko-machine interface	The repeated delays measured in units-tens of minutes
Refusal in access to a telecommunication service	Malfunction of network infrastructure GSM-R	Possible decrease in timeliness because of delays of reception of the important order, communication loss for a while to 20 s
Problems of registration of a rolling stock at crossing of national borders	Defect of procedure of the international roaming, caused by distinctions in service regulations	Communication losses on the considerable area of radio covering GSM-R and considerable delays (15 - 30 minutes on 1 train)
Incorrect addressing by individual (emergency) call DNC→TCHM	Wrong definition honeycombs in which there is a train	Call DNC has been directed in honeycombs which the caused train already left, increase of probability of occurrence of dangerous events because of non-receipt of the important order
Refusal of transfer of emergency call GSM-R	Malfunction of equipment IPC (because of damage at train wreck on a stone talus	Communication loss. TCHM it was possible to transfer DNC only a call «112» by usual phone GSM. A delay of transfer of a call «112» about 20 minutes
	Hindrances from public networks GSM	Delay at performance of a recovery work

Refusals and failures	The reasons	Consequences
Refusal of transfer of a group call, interruption of group connection	Hindrances from public networks GSM	Some collisions at shunting works (without human victims, but with considerable potential of their occurrence)
Refusal of transfer of individual th call GSM-R		Delay at performance of shunting works
Problems of transfer of connection at crossing of national borders	Imperfection of procedure of transfer of connection	Increase of probability of occurrence of dangerous events because of delays of reception of the important order
		Possible decrease in timeliness because of delays of reception of the important order, communication loss for a while to 20 s

CONCLUSION

Now in operation there is a most part of the floor equipment and the cable networks demanding constant maintenance service and repair. To improve position it is possible only at the expense of application of modern means and to the attentive approach to each of the parties of all technological process.

Technical requirements to the organization of high-speed movement: definition of a site and speed of structure; the fast and high-quality organization of all kinds of communication; safety control in a mode of real time; the optimum organization shunting and repair work; throughput increase; time reduction of a finding in a way of high-speed trains; quality improvement of passenger service; introduction of the newest innovative technologies.

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